

**IMPACTUL TRADUCERILOR TEHNICE
ASUPRA EXPERIENȚEI UTILIZATORULUI:
CAZUL LOCALIZĂRII MICROSOFT OFFICE ÎN LIMBA ROMÂNĂ /
THE IMPACT OF TECHNICAL TRANSLATIONS ON USER EXPERIENCE:
THE CASE OF MICROSOFT OFFICE LOCALIZATION INTO ROMANIAN**

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In the current context of accelerated digitalization, software localization is no longer a matter of linguistic transfer alone, but a complex process of cultural and functional adaptation with direct implications for user experience (UX). This article examines the influence of technical translations on how Romanian-speaking users interact with the Romanian-language interface of Microsoft Office LTSC Professional Plus 2024.

The primary objective is to identify problematic linguistic formulations – ambiguous, overly literal, or contextually inadequate – and to assess their effects on the clarity, efficiency, and predictability of user interaction. The study adopts a mixed-method approach, combining a comparative analysis of terminology between the Romanian and English versions of the software with an observational investigation conducted within the academic course "Information and Communication Technologies". Qualitative data, collected from feedback provided by students in non-IT fields, enabled a direct correlation between localization deficiencies and practical usability challenges. The results indicate that inadequate translations can compromise both the functionality and accessibility of software, particularly for users with limited digital literacy. The conclusions underscore the need for rigorous localization processes supported by collaboration between linguists, technical translators, software developers, and UX professionals. The article offers a set of recommendations aimed at improving software localization, emphasizing terminological consistency, linguistic clarity, and cultural appropriateness.